

TABLE-1

Ethyl- β -arylamino-crotonate -CuCl ₂ complex	M. P. with Decomposition	Magnetic moment in B.M.	MW		% Chloride		% Copper		Molar conductance in mhos
			Rast's method Obs.	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1anilino . .	138-140°C	*1.54	385	339.5	20.79	20.91	18.61	18.71	16.64
22-methyl-anilino . .	111-115°C	1.56	396	353.5	20.22	20.08	17.85	17.99	17.54
33-methyl-anilino . .	119-121°C	1.55	392	353.5	20.16	20.08	17.76	17.99	17.96
44-methyl-anilino . .	131-132°C	1.57	374	353.5	20.12	20.08	17.96	17.99	18.00
53-chloro-anilino . .	152-153°C	1.50	405	373.9	18.82	18.99	16.79	16.94	17.78
64-chloro-anilino . .	149-150°C	1.50	396	373.9	18.84	18.99	16.86	16.94	17.96

due to photo oxidation-reduction². The spectrophotometric measurements using Job's method, mole ratio method and slope ratio method indicate the composition of the complexes as 1 : 1³.

These complexes have been prepared by mixing equimolar (0.03M) alcoholic solutions of the chloride and the respective crotonate, when fine green crystals separated after half an hour. They are sparingly soluble in alcohol. Their magnetic moments were determined by using Guoy method and copper and chlorine by the usual methods. The analytical data are given in the table-1.

The low conductance values indicate their non-electrolytic nature and lower magnetic moment values have been attributed to dimerisation and some degree of dimerisation has been supported by molecular weight data; such lowering in paramagnetism of Cu(II) complexes is known⁴. The probable structure of the complex is a square plane, copper(II) with d⁹ configuration. The absorption spectrum in alcohol shows a broad band at 540 nm in agreement with D_{4h} symmetry of the Cu(II) complex.

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Dyes as Inhibitors for the Hydrogen Peroxide Decomposition

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HYDROGEN peroxide is a unique metabolite normally produced and destroyed by a wide variety of plants and animals¹. Recently it has been suggested that cancer may originate by the action of an agent which directly or indirectly generates abnormally high concentration of H₂O₂ in the biological system². Furthermore, the lethal function of the biological poisons, which are known to inhibit the decomposition of H₂O₂, can also be attributed to the increase of H₂O₂ concentration in excess of lethal doses³. As very many dyes are well known either as biological poisons or as carcinogens, it is worthwhile to study their effect on the acceleration⁴ as also on the inhibition of H₂O₂ decomposition. In this preliminary note we report the inhibitory power of several groups of dyes viz. phthaleins, triphenyl methanes, thiazines etc.

Experimental

To have an idea of the inhibitory power of the dyes (listed in Table 1) we measured the rate of oxygen evolution from hydrogen peroxide solution both in the presence and absence of dyes under similar conditions and specially at the same pH (viz., pH 7) to avoid any pH effect. To verify the inhibitory power of the dyes from a different angle we measured the H₂O₂ concentration iodometrically in the original and final solutions. The changes in O.D values were determined by a Hilger U V speck spectrophotometer. It is evident from Table 1 that these dyes are very effective inhibitors for H₂O₂

decomposition. The order of the change in color of the dyes is: Malachite Green > Methyl Violet > Fluorescein > Floxine > Methylene Blue > Safranin > Auramine.

hypothesis that they are converted into hydrated peroxides as

TABLE 1

Concentration of dye = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$. Concentration of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 2.0 (M)$ Temperature = 35°C , $\text{pH} = 7$

Sl No.	Dyes as inhibitors	Amt. of O_2 liberated in (c.c.)		Change in O.D. value in	
		1 day	7 days	1 day	7 days
1	Blank	3.5	55		
2	Malachite Green	0.0	0.5	Nil	90.6%
3	Auramine	0.0	1.0	..	39.5%
4	Methyl Violet	0.0	1.2	..	57.8%
5	Safranin	0.0	1.5	..	40.0%
6	Methylene Blue	0.5	2.5	..	61.7%
7	Floxine	1.0	6.0	..	63.9%
8	Fluorescein	1.0	8.0	..	78.3%

To have a clear idea of the inhibitory power of the dye Auramine, a short kinetic analysis was performed on the decomposition of H_2O_2 . The experimental technique used involved the gas evolution method. The value of the rate constant (k) was determined from the slope of plot of $-\log (V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. time t , where V_∞ and V_t are respectively the initial total volume of O_2 in the H_2O_2 solution and that liberated after the interval of a certain time t . Energy of activation (E_a) of the reaction was determined from the slope of the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$, where T is the temperature ($^\circ\text{K}$). The results obtained are given in Table 2. The large difference in k and E_a values between control and experimental samples illustrates well the high inhibitory power of Auramine.

TABLE 2

Concn. of H_2O_2 (M)	Concn. of Auramine (M)	Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$k(\text{Dye}) \times 10^7$	$k(\text{Blank}) \times 10^7$	$E_a(\text{Dye})$ kcal/mole	$E_a(\text{Blank})$ kcal/mole
		40	0.614	3.839		
4.0	3×10^{-4}	45	0.690	9.298	55.73	28.2
		50	0.776	17.60		

Results and Discussion

Mechanism: Stabilization of H_2O_2 by some metal oxides has been interpreted on the basis of the

which are effective stabilising agents, and if the proportion of metal oxide to H_2O_2 is such as to lead to incomplete metal peroxide formation, there will be either feeble stabilization or a slight acceleration of the decomposition process⁵. Most of the dyes used in this work contain nitrogen in the chromophoric group. So the possibility of formation of hydrated amine peroxide complexes arises, as formation of such intermediate complexes in the production of N-amine oxide by the action of H_2O_2 on amine (both aliphatic and aromatic) is well known⁶. Thus a similar inhibition mechanism as described may occur. This idea is further corroborated by the observation that in dilute solution of H_2O_2 , very little inhibition of H_2O_2 decomposition was envisaged. However, we could not get any spectrophotometric evidence of such complex formation in our preliminary investigations. Still it is interesting to note that a dye retains its inhibition power strongly even after nearly complete fading of its color after seven days (Table 1). Interestingly enough, we might also be tempted to correlate the fading of color in the dyes (where N forms the chromophoric group) with the formation of amine peroxide complexes thereby destroying the chromophoric N. In the other dyes where there is no nitrogen in the chromophore e.g. in the case of floxine and fluorescein, there is a quinone structure capable of impeding the free radical decomposition process of H_2O_2 . Incidentally they are the least active inhibitors of the dyes studied (Table 1).

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